

IMPORTANT STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR ACHIEVING CURRENCY STABILITY IN UZBEKISTAN

Turg'unov Baxtiyor Nuriddinovich

1. Introduction

Inflation and exchange rate volatility present different challenges for the economy. Exchange rate volatility hampers exports of goods and services, can act as a barrier in the development of a country's economy, and reduce capital inflows. In addition, fluctuating exchange rates due to the depreciation of the national currency in terms of investment significantly increase the cost of servicing external debt. It is an important factor in causing negative consequences for economic growth. Combine by lowering official international reserves and the value of the national currency (so-called burn-through and defense of reserves): with increasing pressure on the foreign exchange market, the national regulator can maintain the stability of the national currency through official sales of reserves and exchange rate control by the local currency.

Today, the problem of maintaining currency stability is particularly relevant. Retention of the national currency, as a key development factor, requires effective measures and solutions. One of the main parameters of the country's economy is the choice of the main strategy for the development of the real exchange rate. The level and pace of development largely depend on the corresponding development of the latter. With the weakening of the national currency exchange rate, domestic enterprises invariably receive advantages in trade and, in general, beat competitors who, in turn, may not have such substantial profit rates at the same level of costs and expensive products. Against the background of the theory of new trade, the effect of currency devaluation changes. Now the nominal exchange rate in the economy is not only the determinant of external competitiveness. Its movement affects both the structure of the economy and the rate of investment in its development, which ultimately affects the

rate of economic growth. Together with the need for a stable currency in the reforming economy, there is a need to predict exchange rate fluctuations. (Nusratovich and Asidakhan2023)(Nor et al., 2020)

1.1. Background of Currency Stability in Uzbekistan

In addition, a decrease in the exchange rate undermines output and income. If the objective is to ensure stability in the current account balance, there are contradictory requirements in each case. It is very difficult to ensure an optimal combination of moderate exchange rate smoothing without endangering the stability of the financial market. This situation can lead to increased speculative pressure, depletion of foreign currency reserves, increased capital outflow, increased demand to meet the existing market price, devaluation of the national currency, and deepening of the crisis phenomena.

Furthermore, independently restoring the exchange rate of the national currency, which has significant economic costs, is associated with excessive speculative activity in the foreign currency market. This becomes a barrier that makes it even more difficult to reduce the level of shifted forms and stabilize the demand for foreign currency. It is known that in case of excess demand for foreign currency, an appreciation of the real exchange rate leads to a worsening of competitiveness, which intensifies the crisis connotations of the economy.

In the highly competitive global economy, the exchange rates of national currencies are closely related to competitiveness. The choice of stability and the direction of strengthening the national currency is based on the aggregate rubric, aimed at increasing profit and strengthening the competitive environment. However, ensuring the stability of the national currency is both labor-consuming and unpredictable, especially when there is a high level of shifted forms that create a stable demand for foreign currency.

2. Monetary Policy Measures

The sale of foreign exchange reserves by individuals has been terminated. Starting from February 19, 2021, the exchange rates of the Uzbek soum are set on the basis of

supply and demand, and trade operations take place without the direct participation of the Central Bank. The measures implemented increase the importance of market factors in the formation of equilibrium exchange rates, the convenience of market players, and the reliability of currency transactions. Measures to liberalize the capital account allow residents of the Republic to operate freely with national and foreign capital both within and outside Uzbekistan. According to Article 34 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Currency Regulation and Currency Control", residents have the right to open bank accounts (deposits) in foreign currency abroad in a freely convertible currency received as income from operations not under the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It was unclear which has been added by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions".

As to the liberalization of currency conversion operations, several measures have been implemented to provide the freedom of movement and the right of ownership to individuals in international funds to their residents. Since July 1, 2020, the lists of goods for which foreign exchange earnings are required to be converted into the national currency have been liquidated. The mandatory sale of foreign exchange earnings to legal and individuals independently producing import goods has been canceled. Besides, the sole method of currency purchase transaction in the domestic foreign exchange market has been established, and the single currency conversion threshold for various operations of legal and individuals has been set. From June 3, 2019 to January 2021, the official exchange rate of Uzbekistan's soum against the US dollar decreased annually without a single stop. Since February, it has slightly increased and stabilized. With the transition to the floating exchange rate of the soum, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan has begun selling currency in the domestic foreign exchange market without a time limit. (Babasyan et al., 2023)(Абдуллаева & Тураева, 2021)(Abdukadirov, 2022)(Cabezon et al.)

2.1. Exchange Rate Management

Uzbekistan's experience in exchange rate management shows that the government follows a fixed exchange rate policy. However, the macroeconomic problems have

shown the necessity of improving the exchange rate system in the transition period of the economy to a more flexible exchange rate regime. The principal concern of exchange rate management policies is to ensure price stability and control inflation, which are significant for both long-term sustainable economic activity and economic growth potential. When the exchange rate is flexible, it is natural for current economic activity to gain importance along with macroeconomic stabilization. The direct effect of exchange rate movements on exports and imports changes is considered as a major ground for economic activity. Furthermore, in the long term, exchange rate decisions are important for determining the equilibrium (natural) foreign exchange level and the sustainability of the current account level.

With the development of the economies of countries and deepening economic reforms, global economic processes have become closely interdependent, and as a result, the stability of the national currency is a crucial and priority indicator for ensuring economic growth and stability in the country. The exchange rate, determined by the interaction of supply and demand in the foreign exchange market, is one of the most important macroeconomic indicators that reflects the economic situation in the country and directly influences other macroeconomic indicators. The exchange rate can be used to measure any financial variables and capital flows between countries.

2.2. Interest Rate Policies

However, from current macroeconomic factors, it does not appear possible to unify exchange rates so quickly and bring them to long-term equilibrium. Even if, in order to determine long-term exchange rate equilibrium, the best method of purchasing parity will be supplemented with appropriate components of exports and imports demanded by respective domestic economies, etc., it will be necessary to bravely deal with short-term instability. Brodrik, based on Diquis' model, finds out that an exchange rate appreciated by 10 percent (or devalued by 10 percent) may, during two years, push inflation up or down by 2.7 percent. It means that if, in order to neutralize inflation pushed out by the exchange rate, money supply will increase or decrease by an appropriate weighted average. The tools of money supply searching are traditional

deposits. If the population and businesses expect the dynamics of money cost to be in accordance with the above-mentioned numbers, then actual interest rates and nominal effective exchange rates do not substantially change. After all, both of these parameters may fluctuate daily due to the imperfection of assumptions, price adjustments when market operation, of large magnitude. (Doojav et al., 2024)

When selecting an interest rate policy, it is necessary to give a clear answer to three questions: which interest rate needs to be regulated, how to perform this regulation, and how the central bank will influence the chosen rate. In macroeconomic aspect, interest and exchange rates are closely connected, as both of them are created by demand and supply. Exchange rate equilibrium is considered to be a cornerstone of any economy, as a high exchange rate is essential for lowering inflation, export restrictions, reducing imports, and reducing external debt. One can say that a high exchange rate indirectly is the "father of high interest rate".

2.3. Reserve Management

Thus, increasing the independence reserve management and, on its basis, developing appropriate monetary policy instruments by increasing the proportion of international reserves that reflect the income and wealth of the entire population, that is, the sovereign gold and foreign exchange reserves of the Central Bank, will create conditions for increasing the sustainability of the currency and increasing incomes of the general population. When the living standards increase increasingly, the one-time and final types of demand will address the many issues not only of inflation, investment and trade deficits, but also of the sustainability of the currency. Therefore, just as the Central Bank plays an increasingly important role in the formation of a new pension system in Uzbekistan, on the other hand, reasonable proposals could be made to further improve reserve management. In order to enhance the independence of the reserve management of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, they will be clearly defined in the above-mentioned concept based on the principle of transparency and funding, and to reduce the possibility of abuse in the implementation of universal international documents, and to further improve the Framework Convention process.

Optimal management of the state's gold and foreign exchange reserves, which accounts for more than a quarter of the international reserves of all countries in the world, increases the creditworthiness and stability of the currency. The independence and soundness of the Central Bank's gold and foreign exchange reserves is the result of focused efforts to maintain the nominal stability of the national currency, promote domestic savings in foreign currency and the liberalization of foreign exchange regulation, create a clear and transparent macroeconomic and financial system, and widely promote the activities of the Central Bank. If there are reserves independent of the state budget, it is possible to manipulate the macroeconomic impact of the statutory and compulsory reserves of the central bank. However, 30% of the reserve assets are of such a nature, that is, they do not reflect the soundness of the financial and economic situation in the country, and are directed to the state budget to fund the budget deficit.

3. Structural Reforms

The formation of the medium-term program budget and the comprehensive conversion of the enterprise sector to the self-financing system were the first steps to overcome the inflation and currency crisis. Short-term requires the creation of prerequisites for replacing the current administrative methods of price regulation with market mechanisms. The formation in the broad sections of the population of rules of conduct based on an understanding of economic relations excludes various fraudulent schemes for enrichment. In a relatively short time, citizens must understand such simple things - how much wealth they possess, which of them are of high, medium, and low exchange value, which should be spent when buying various goods. Impact in this direction is essential in relation to business entities.

Any structural reform of the economy will have a serious impact on the level of production, consumption, and hence on the price level. Therefore, changes in the structure of the economy should be made taking into account the basic principles of the planned price policy, which provides for strict control over all expenditures. The transition to predominance of market principles in pricing cannot but have an impact on the high rates of inflation typical of countries with economies in transition.

3.1. Financial Sector Development

Today, it is common knowledge that market instruments are based on direct sales and economically vital powerful volume credit agencies, which have mutually supposing quantity. So, it is necessary to create conditions when the bank with the size and the system of foreign currency reserves can be secured and can act to stop the shrinkage of the local currency in the regions. With that, such actions of banking mechanisms substantially do not have to worsen their position in terms of replacement of the resource base with the population by the states. In socially oriented reforms, the financial institutions demonstrate their preference for the population, limited in the means, and act as a tool to protect and promote its interests of solidarity. At the same time, to restore the lost prestige of the bank's structures will undoubtedly be possible also through their own active work, but only by the policy of working the tsar on the regional stock exchanges. Because, so the determinant's right of banks increases, which are getting involved in the volume of stock exchanges, especially in the real sector of the economy.

One of the important trends of integration of Uzbekistan into the global economic environment is the development of the financial market. Therefore, currently one of the most important points in the banking system of Uzbekistan is the multiple inflation and macroeconomic destabilization. The banking system plays a key role in the complex of measures to ensure stability of the national currency and macroeconomics of Uzbekistan. The economic essence of the banking system in the market management mechanism is that, together with the Central Bank, it forms the very economical institutional complex of principles of market management of the economy. This defines the necessity to conduct joint monetary policy with the Central Bank, especially in terms of managing the local currency. In the case of the simultaneous functioning of bank deposits in the bank networks and banking systems, there are large differences in their development and functioning. It is necessary to reconstruct and establish the banks and banking systems in parallel. But working only through the central banks still cannot meet the quantitative and qualitative needs in cash in the industrial economy by

banking systems. Therefore, there is a paradoxical situation in which, parallel to the fear of the collapse of banks, there is also the inevitable withdrawal of settlements by the population in cash and possible depreciation of the low-dollar (gaps shilling). Thus, undoubtedly, the important role of independent and comprehensive stabilization, but not so much as necessary up to total failure creation. This interaction demands the joint improvement and perfection of operating principles with market tools. Such principles should be worked out through cautious consideration of existing in advanced market economy.

3.2. Trade and Investment Liberalization

At the same time, the implementation of this strategic direction leads to currency stability. Long-term and systematic work in liberal and structural policy, as well as the natural weaknesses of developed market countries. The fact that these issues are a consequence, not a cause of instability, should not allow politicians and professional performers to act in the same spirit of history, which was the history of fixed rates over the centuries, fighting global instability, the relationship between them and exchange transactions remain irrelevant. We have been told that we have long given up on using the cyclical exchange rate. However, they are less clear. The wave is always smooth, but in practice there is no need to pretend that this is the result of a government decision, as is often the case. Central banks and governments cannot freely manipulate domestic prices and evidence. As already mentioned, a currency cannot rely solely on the US dollar to ensure currency stability. Improvements in the exchange rate over time lead to a long wave, especially with countries that integrate the exchanges.

Trade and investment liberalization: reducing state domination in external trade and investment receipts. This strategic direction includes aspects such as establishing uniform economic conditions for all economic entities, developing individual measures to stimulate exports and attract foreign investments and technologies, enhancing investment policy and measures designed to meet key demands of the investment environment, and steadily transforming the balance of payment from labor and investment receipts without state investment and trade protectionism to a self-

regulating market mechanism. Foreign trade and investment policy is becoming an integral part of economic development, intended to attract financial, investment, and technology resources from abroad.

3.3. Fiscal Discipline

Fiscal discipline ensures financial stability, which boosts households' trust in the national currency, that is of crucial importance for the effectiveness of the operating mechanisms of monetary policy at this stage. Thus, any steps to relax fiscal policy in favor of absorbing liquidity through the placement of public debt on the domestic market should be carried out in compliance with macroeconomic indicators. Theoretical and practical importance in the mechanism of state budgetary policy should be the counter-cyclical nature of the budget rule, i.e., the ability of the budget policy either to soften the cyclical fluctuations of the economy or to restrain the cyclical development of the economy. Moreover, a transparent and predictable fiscal policy should ensure stability of the tax base by means of clear and single tax legislation, which envisages equal and indiscriminate treatment for all economic agents during tax administration.

A mandatory condition for effective monetary policy is the existence of fiscal discipline. In recent years, the government has pursued a policy of maintaining fiscal discipline, which resulted in a positive impact on the country's economy and the domestic money market. According to our calculations, in 2017-2019, the direct impact of state budgetary policy on narrowing the difference between inflation and currency depreciation should be assessed in the range of 0.1-0.7 percent. Thus, fiscal discipline, ensuring the continued sustainable operation of the monetary authorities, acts as a goal and condition, limiting their field of activity.

References:

Nusratovich, S. K., & Asidakhan, A. (2023). STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN. QO ‘QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 9, 7-10. kokanduni.uz

Nor, M. I., Masron, T. A., & Alabdullah, T. T. Y. (2020). Macroeconomic fundamentals and the exchange rate volatility: empirical evidence from Somalia. SAGE Open. [sagepub.com](https://www.sagepub.com)

Babasyan, D., Gu, Y., & Melecky, M. (2023). Late banking transitions: Comparing Uzbekistan to earlier reformers. World Development Perspectives. [\[HTML\]](#)

Абдуллаева, М & Тураева, С (2021). The development of exchange rate systems in Central Asia-history and current policy initiatives. Общество и инновации. inscience.uz

Abdukadirov, B. (2022). of Industrialization in Uzbekistan. [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net)

Cabazon, E., Mirzayev, S., & Al-Farah, R. (). Macroeconomic Policies to Enhance Financial Stability in the Caucasus and Central Asia. [imf.org](https://www.imf.org). [imf.org](https://www.imf.org)

Doojav, G. O., Purevdorj, M., & Batjargal, A. (2024). The macroeconomic effects of exchange rate movements in a commodity-exporting developing economy. International Economics. [\[HTML\]](#)